

Improving the Quality of Literature Teaching Based on Technological Techniques in Higher Educational Institutions

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Abstract: this article will talk about the problems of effective teaching of subjects in higher education with the help of Information Technology and the peculiarities of improving the quality of Education. A new approach aimed at the educational process is reflected on the influence of innovative methods, modern methods aimed at improving the quality of training of interactive actions.

Keywords: innovative education, innovation, interactive methods, pedagogical innovation, question-based learning method.

Introduction

As mankind lives in this harmonious time, it moves towards the news, towards the construction of a new modern life. Education also expects innovation from a person, if he does not renew it, if he does not bring it to life, he will gradually lose his strength. Currently, educational institutions demand creativity, elegance, hard work, new heights from young students. In order to radically improve the quality of training, today we will think with you about innovative technologies, interactive methods, innovative education.

We know that innovative technologies include innovative methods, and innovative methods include innovative research. Let's clarify what the word innovation is in it:

The concept of innovation is derived from the English innovation meaning innovation, invention. And in the educational process, the essence of this word is the exchange of quantity towards quality, that is, a strong level of quality, which is a combination of terms in which interactive actions in training are expressed through opportunities for expressing thought, reforming life experiences, new and effective approaches and strategies.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

On the research of this topic, there are scientific works dedicated to improving the educational system of foreign and Country scientists, methods of applying information technology in the teaching of subjects and improving the quality of teaching in higher education.

Today, higher education is developing in conditions of strong competition. The correct location of activity is the most important success factor in the market. The quality of education is decisive in the competitive struggle of domestic and foreign universities.

Pedagogical innovations are used in order to show positive changes in the relevant field, to

achieve qualitatively high results. The interpretation of this type of innovation is reflected in the following steps:

Stage 1. Birth of a new idea (discovery phase);

Stage 2. Justification of innovation with reference to a new idea;

Stage 3. Practical use of grounded innovation;

Stage 4. The spread of the novelty and its wide application to practice;

Stage 5. The dominance of novelty in the relevant field;

Stage 6. Alternative.

The innovative educational stages mentioned above serve as an important factor in improving the quality, productivity of education if used in training.

Today, a number of problems remain that are becoming an obstacle to improving the quality of education in higher educational institutions, comprehensive reforms carried out in the Republic, ensuring the active participation of these institutions in updates in the social and economic spheres, in particular:

- first, the process of organizing training in the higher education system, the fact that the system for assessing the knowledge of students studying does not meet the requirements of today;
- secondly, the fact that there is no modern system for assessing the activities, knowledge and pedagogical skills of professors;
- thirdly, the fact that the entrance test questions to higher educational institutions do not allow to determine the ability of the applicant to think logically;
- fourth, the presence of problems in the admission of talented young people to higher educational institutions;
- fifth, the lack of effective public control over the educational process in higher education institutions;
- sixth, the survival of corruption cases in higher education institutions;
- seventh, the imperceptible participation and initiative of higher education institutions in the comprehensive and systematic changes carried out in the country;
- eighth, the failure of the active participation of higher education institutions in explaining the content and essence of the fundamental reforms carried out in our republic to our people, the general public through the media;
- ninth, that higher education institutions have not become centers of communication that exchange ideas with innovative and technological ideas, that the necessary conditions have not been created for teachers, young scientists and students to take the initiative in order to systematically study, analyze and propose solutions to existing problems and shortcomings in the relevant fields, etc.

Currently, during the lesson, educators are applying new pedagogical technologies. This greatly contributes to the thorough acquisition of knowledge in the educational process, as well as the increase in skills and qualifications.

Pedagogical technology is a collaborative unity of the designed process, methods of principles, means of education, ensuring the integrity, success of activities, results, a task that rests on social, didactic, mental-pedagogical, philosophical theory in setting and achieving a goal based on a scientific concept.

The introduction of new pedagogical technologies into the educational implementation process is based on:

- ensuring the mastery of the personality of the student involved in the educational process;
- implementation of the achievement (guaranteed) of the result of the educational goal;
- a means of providing educational content, bringing the technology of method forms into a single system.

In teaching theory, it is impossible to distinguish new pedagogical and information technologies from each other, since the widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies will change the new educational paradigm and provide only modern information technologies with the effective use of the capabilities of new pedagogical technologies.

The organization of educational activities at the moment requires the student to calculate both with the complex of daily subjects and with the complex of assignments on them. This creates many problems in practice. In such conditions, students cannot focus all their attention on any particular subject, which is taken separately (which is very interesting in itself). In these cases, in our eyes, modular teaching is the best solution.

The use of knowledge is the most important issue. In the process of intensive education, the educational information that the student must master includes facts, phenomena, processes, laws, methods of action. For each of these components of information, the most personal goals of assimilation can be formed.

The main manifestations of innovation are: new ideas, specific goals aimed at changing the system or direction of activity, unconventional approaches, unusual initiatives, advanced work methods.

Innovative education in turn is reflected in the use of innovative methods, that is, interactive methods. One of the important requirements for the organization of modern education is to achieve high results in a short time, without excessive mental and physical exertion. Between short periods of time, the supply of certain theoretical knowledge to students, the formation of skills and qualifications in them from a certain activity, as well as the control of the activities of students, the assessment of the level of knowledge, skills, qualifications acquired by them requires a high pedagogical skill from the teacher as well as a new approach to the educational process.

Pedagogical technology in its essence has a subjective nature, that is, each pedagogical educational and educational process should be creatively organized without its own possibility, based on professional skills. Pedagogical technologies, regardless of what form, method and means they are organized using:

- increase the effectiveness of pedagogical activity;
- determination of interaction between teacher and students;
- thorough knowledge of educational subjects by students ensure occupation;
- formation of independent, free and creative thinking skills in students;
- necessary for students to be able to realize their potential creating conditions;

The mental attack method serves to ensure the activity of students in the process of training, to encourage them to think freely and free them from the inertia of the same thinking, to collect colorful ideas on a particular topic, as well as to teach them to overcome thoughts that arise at the initial stage of the process of solving creative tasks.

In addition one of the techniques that encourage intelligence is inquiry-based learning what if learning is question-based? It is about this request-based education. In this approach, the teacher directs students to develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills. To learn these skills, the teacher helps students reflect on their processes, teaches them possible approaches, and encourages them to try different methods. Students are encouraged to fail as part of the process and then improve their performance in further activities. Instead of students repeating the answers taught, students learn to look for answers to the questions themselves. Thus, students develop strong research skills. In addition, children learn how to choose questions to answer and what questions they can ask. This approach is also aimed at students because it requires active student participation. The teacher guides and teaches, but students also help with the choice of study topics. This method is considered one of the innovative educational methods to attack the mind by asking questions through critical thinking.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that the introduction of new pedagogical technologies into the educational process is a requirement of the period. This work depends on the science teacher. In turn, it is advisable for the educator to be creative, implement various forms, methods of new pedagogical technologies, skillfully support them in the educational process and use them effectively. In this, of course, the quality of the educational process increases, which, in turn, plays an important role in the training of mature, competitive personnel in every possible way.

Based on the results of the study, the following proposals are being made:

- any applied innovative or pedagogical technology must necessarily correspond to the content, quality of education and have a high effect on its assimilation;
- the subjects taught should be in line with the direction of the student and have a high effect that adds to his mastery; - To determine the capabilities of Information Technology in ensuring the quality of Education;
- For the stages of education, it is necessary to create category electronic textbooks from all disciplines and place them on an existing electronic platform;
- any pedagogical technologies used in the teaching of science should have opportunities to help assimilate the content of education and make a good impression on the student.

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